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PEDAGOGICAL BURNOUT AMONG UNIVERSITY TEACHERS AND CONDITIONS FOR ITS PREVENTION

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Abstract. The article examines various manifestations of professional burnout. increased anxiety, a sense of incompetence, loss of motivation to work and innovate, emotional and nervous exhaustion, as well as indifference and devaluation of pedagogical activity, and based on the disclosure of the essence and content of the process of pedagogical prevention of professional burnout among university teachers, the conditions for pedagogical prevention of professional burnout among university teachers are substantiated. The author believes that a comprehensive structure should be taken into account, covering: the identification of risk factors that cause burnout among university teachers and ways to effectively prevent this phenomenon; teaching teachers methods of pedagogical prevention of burnout; improving the system of pedagogical support for higher school teachers.

Introduction

In the modern educational environment, despite progressive changes such as increased attention to the individual, the introduction of digital technologies, and a personalized approach to learning, university teachers are increasingly facing various manifestations of professional burnout. This includes heightened anxiety, feelings of incompetence, loss of motivation for work and innovation, emotional and nervous exhaustion, as well as indifference and devaluation of teaching activities. Professional burnout of educators is a complex of symptoms that arises from prolonged stress and leads to the depletion of emotional, energetic, and personal resources of the specialist [Erkinbekova, 2012].

Studying the causes and developing prevention methods for pedagogical burnout is especially important in the current conditions when the professional activities of teachers are undergoing significant transformations. It is necessary to investigate the main aspects, content, and structure of the pedagogical prevention process of this phenomenon.

The goal of this work is to determine the essence and content of the pedagogical prevention process of professional burnout among higher education teachers.

Main part. The development of pedagogical burnout occurs when a teacher feels a lack of professional competencies and senses a mismatch between their personal qualities and the demands of the profession, as well as the social expectations imposed by society, colleagues, and university management.

Special studies (M.Sh. Aldieva, T.A. Bergis, I.B. Burtovaya, N.G. Osukhova, V.E. Orlov, E.A. Solovyova, and others) indicate that burnout is one of the ways through which a teacher loses professional adaptation, as well as a cause for various negative professional changes. The concept of “burnout” was first used in the 1970s thanks to

research conducted by H.J. Freudenberger. Professional burnout is considered a prolonged response to stress or as a syndrome that develops as a result of prolonged exposure to moderately strong professional stressors.

The following negative manifestations are characteristic of burnout syndrome:

- exhaustion of the emotional sphere (significant reduction in emotional activity, nervous and mental exhaustion, apathy or emotional overload, loss of interest in work activities, loss of understanding of the value of life, etc.);
- depersonalization (disruption of normal interpersonal relationships, increased negative attitudes towards others, aggressiveness, tactlessness, and other similar manifestations);
- reduction in the significance of personal achievements (devaluation of successes in the professional sphere, decline in self-esteem and self-respect, feeling of one's own incompetence, etc.).

Recently, the interrelationship and mutual influence of occupational stress and emotional burnout syndrome among educational workers have been increasingly discussed. [Egoryshev, 2023].

In the absence of a rational approach to their application in stressful situations, a lack of active and effective difficulty coping skills, and the absence of a supportive system, the educator begins to feel signs of stress at various levels: emotional, behavioral, and cognitive.

In this regard, it becomes particularly important to study the essence of pedagogical prevention of professional burnout, viewed as a purposeful and specially organized educational process that prepares higher education teachers to overcome the impact of professional disadaptation mechanisms on their personality by developing professional skills aimed at combating burnout.

To understand the essence of pedagogical prevention of professional burnout among university teachers, it is necessary to consider a comprehensive structure that includes: identifying risk factors that cause burnout in higher education teachers, and ways to effectively prevent this phenomenon; training teachers in methods of

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pedagogical prevention of burnout; improving the system of pedagogical support for higher education teachers. Based on the study of factors contributing to professional burnout (low salaries of young teachers - 76%, increased demands from administration - 58%, the factor of teachers' unpreparedness for innovative trends such as the digitalization of education, etc. - 71%), the study presents a systematized structure of pedagogical prevention of burnout among university teachers, in terms of subjects, objects, forms, techniques, methods, means, functions, patterns, contradictions, goals and objectives, principles, and results aimed at preventing the development of burnout.

The structure defines both commonly accepted principles of the pedagogical process and specific preventive principles, for example, the structurally-dynamic principle, which takes into account the integrity and systemic nature of the professional burnout process. This allows for the assessment of risk factors for the development of the phenomenon in question, considering the characteristics of professional activities and the interconnection of all areas, functions, and processes of the teachers' psyche. The principle based on the harmonious development of each teacher's professional skills is also taken into account, considering the relationship with the requirements of functional roles, as well as the principle of effectiveness, continuity, systematicness, and dynamism of pedagogical preventive activities in this area.

As part of our work, a specialized program called "Pedagogical Prevention of Professional Burnout for University Teachers" has been developed. This program is implemented in three phases: initial assessment, a series of sessions, and final evaluation. The series of sessions consists of three modules. The first module focuses on self-assessment of burnout levels, acquiring knowledge and skills related to the specifics of pedagogical work in the context of current trends in higher education (such as humanization, individualization, and digitalization), as well as understanding the negative aspects of professional activities that lead to maladaptation. The second module aims to form an understanding of the essence, content, and structure of burnout prevention, teaching self-regulation methods, developing positive thinking,

and skills for self-help in crisis situations.

The third module focuses on the development of three levels of professional competence, mastering self-correction techniques in stressful situations, motivation for creativity and self-improvement, improving interaction with colleagues, supporting teachers, and expanding the scope of cultural leisure. In the framework of this work, the effectiveness of pedagogical prevention of burnout among university faculty is determined based on the following criteria and indicators:

a) Organizational-methodological aspect (the number of independently implemented actions in key areas of work; the ability to effectively perform duties when teaching students, using effective tools such as virtual classrooms, online services, and personalized learning systems that create a favorable educational atmosphere in accordance with the demands of the time and the needs of each student; striving for professional growth; the quality of materials presented in methodological sessions aimed at preventing professional burnout);

b) Substantive aspect (the degree of professional and personal independence in resolving current work issues; motivation to improve one's professional and general cultural level; balance between external and internal motivation to work and a creative approach in the profession; psychological-pedagogical competence and overall cultural level);

c) Resultative aspect (the results of a comprehensive assessment of achievements in professional activities; knowledge of legal acts and orders, mastery of professional methods and techniques in the field of preventing professional burnout; development of self-control, self-correction, and psych hygiene skills; the degree of burnout among university teachers, established based on diagnostic procedures).

Thus, within the framework of the research aimed at identifying key directions and factors that contribute to improving the effectiveness of pedagogical prevention of professional burnout among university teachers, the task of optimizing the psychological and pedagogical training of higher education specialists for implementing this prevention was addressed.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that the effectiveness of the proposed system of pedagogical prevention of professional burnout among university teachers is ensured by the following pedagogical conditions:

- conducting practical classes in groups included in the system of pedagogical prevention to form an understanding of the essence, content, and structure of pedagogical prevention among university teachers;
- integration into the targeted program "Pedagogical Prevention of Professional Burnout Among Higher Education Teachers" of a complex of knowledge about the nature, content, and structure of burnout prevention, with an emphasis on training in innovative strategies for overcoming professional stress;
- the use of problem-oriented learning methods in professional training processes that contribute to the formation of an individual professional style, awareness of the directions for developing professional competencies, defining the trajectory of professional growth, and stimulating the creative activity of educators; ©
- the use of various techniques by the administration and educators of educational institutions to activate preventive work among teachers;
- the formation of a negative attitude towards the development of burnout syndrome among university educators;
- the mastering of a comprehensive system of methods, techniques, and self-preventive technologies (self-regulation, self-correction, self-diagnosis, psycho-sparing technologies, psycho-hygiene, self-control, etc.) by educators;
- the realization by higher education teachers of their role in the independent prevention of professional burnout; © the integration of real problems faced by educators into the educational process of teacher training.

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